

DMP-Review and Guidelines

DATA STEWARDSHIP – EXERCISE 2

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Introduction

Data Management Plans (DMPs) play an important role in ensuring the effective management, preservation, and sharing of research data. As the research landscape continues to evolve, it is essential to critically evaluate the existing DMPs and identify areas where improvements can be made. This report aims to present a systematic and structured analysis of published DMPs, highlighting common shortcomings and good examples, while also assessing their adherence to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles.

The purpose of this analysis is to provide constructive feedback and guidelines to fellow researchers, both current and future, who are participating in the course “Data Stewardship”. By understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the DMPs, we can collectively enhance the quality and effectiveness of future submissions. Additionally, this report will serve as a valuable resource for the broader research community, promoting better data stewardship practices.

To undertake this analysis, we have evaluated DMPs shared by participants, containing diverse domains and research disciplines. Furthermore, we have leveraged the Science Europe Guidance for Reviewers and the FAIRsFAIR guidance to establish comprehensive evaluation criteria.

Our report will adopt both quantitative and qualitative analyses. Through a careful examination of each question and section within the DMPs, we will identify common shortcomings and good examples, shedding light on areas where improvements are needed.

In addition to evaluating the content of DMPs, we will assess the publication and data sharing practices described within them. Evaluating whether the published data meets the FAIR criteria will allow us to gauge the degree to which researchers are embracing the principles of openness, accessibility, and interoperability. This analysis will enable us to provide specific recommendations for enhancing the “FAIRness” of published data.

Note: We omitted the assessment of our own DMPs in this report.

Common Shortcomings

The DMP-Submissions were generally inconsistent with the assignment description across the board. This includes missing repositories & artifacts and no provided DOIs. Notably 8 of the 13 evaluated DMPs had issues in “Storage & Backup” as well as “Data Sharing & Long-Term Preservation” as can be seen in the DMP Evaluation Summary.

Evaluation

For this evaluation, we granted up to 10 points for each category, resulting in a total of 100 possible points.

FAIR

In this category, a total of 40 points could be achieved. On average, 26 points were awarded. Filtering out statistical outliers result in a mean value of 32 points. The best results are achieved in the category “Accessible”, with an average value of 7.62 points. The most room for improvement is in the category “Reusable”, with an average value of 5.31 points.

Overall, the DMPs show good results when assessed according to FAIR guidelines.

Honorable Mention

No DMP managed to get assessed a perfect score, however the following examples provide a solid work in each category in the conducted FAIR evaluation:

*Analysis of correlation between water pollution in Höfen and Covid-19 cases in Austria in 2020*¹

*Correlating change in asparagus plant area to GDP growth*²

*Naive Bayes Sentiment Analysis*³

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7930720>

² <https://zenodo.org/record/7934356>

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/7934574>

Findable

A common issue is that no DOI for used repositories or output data is provided in the DMP. Also, tags should be used more frequently to ensure better findability. Most reports mention the use of a cloud service for data backup but did not provide any documentation on where to find these backups.

Accessible

The issues discussed in the previous section carry over to the assessment for accessibility. Some experiments did not publish the output data but only provide the source code, others did not add the links to the report and only provide them within readme-files or the source code itself. For the processed data, some sources are only linked generally (e.g., the landing page of the source, but not the actual data).

Interoperable

The assignment for interoperability stated to provide output data in a format which scores at least 3 stars in the 5-star model⁴. Three out of 15 works submitted did not meet this requirement, providing either no output data at all or in a proprietary format (e.g, excel files). Other common shortcomings are missing descriptions on the output data, which makes interoperability harder for future work utilizing the produced datasets.

Reusable

Points mentioned in the previous section also apply for reusability. The biggest issue is missing description of output datasets, which make further processing infeasible. For cases where no output dataset is provided, programming knowledge is required to produce the datasets.

⁴ <https://5stardata.info/en/>

Science Europe Guide

Following the FAIR evaluation, we also specifically evaluated the DMPs provided with the Science Europe Guidelines in mind. We looked at each section in detail and granted up to 10 points.

Honorable Mention

No DMP managed to get assessed a perfect score, however the following examples provide a solid work in each category in the conducted Science Europe Guide evaluation:

*Retrieval and Analysis of ASCAT and ISMN Data for Soil Moisture Estimation DMP*⁵

*Naive Bayes Sentiment Analysis*⁶

*Evaluation of a simple score-based Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithm*⁷

*Analysis of global emissions and natural disasters from 1960 to 2021*⁸

*Algorithms performance comparison in a classification task*⁹

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/7933523>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/7934574>

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/7932513>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/7934981>

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7935068>

Data Description and Collection or Re-Use of Existing Data

Some of the research data provided were just generic links to the website the data was scraped from and not the actual data itself. In such cases it was also not quite clear on how exactly the data was fetched (we had to look at the code or the github repo).

A common mistake was the size estimation of the input and output data (100MB), which comes from the DMP-Generator and was not consistent with the actual size of the data.

Documentation and Data Quality

In a lot of cases the DMPs stated that the quality of the research data will be checked and reviewed but no detailed explanation was provided.

Storage and Backup during the Research Process

Some DMPs were missing a GitHub repo or did not provide a link to it. A lot of DMPs were mentioning the TU.it as a backup and storage solution but again did not provide actual links to the data. Many DMPs were also missing DOIs for input and output data across the board.

Legal and Ethical Requirements, Codes of Conduct

None of the provided DMPs had any real legal or ethical concerns. This section was mostly comprised of boilerplate statements and/or relisting of the licensing of the research data.

Data Sharing and Long-Term Preservation

A common mistake was that the output data from the experiment (CSVs, plots) were not provided anywhere or did not get DOIs assigned. The same can be said for the input data as it was not persisted anywhere except for the original source or somewhere in the GitHub repo without any DOIs.

Generally speaking, only very few DMPs provided an actual second party repository other than GitHub for long term preservation.

Data Management Responsibilities and Resources

This section was entirely comprised of boilerplate statements from the DMP-Generator and thus sufficient for the size & purpose of the provided DMPs.

Guidelines based on the shortcomings

Most of the problems could have been avoided by reading the task description carefully in detail and following the provided Science Europe Guidelines.

Additionally, we condensed the most important shortcomings to the following points:

1. Provide an overview of the input & output data in a tabular form.
 - a. If research data cannot be accessed publicly, state **in the DMP** how to access it **in detail**.
 - b. Give correct size estimations.
 - c. **Backup** your input and output data and **generate DOIs**.
2. **Provide a simple explanation of what your experiment does.**
3. State what exactly the experiment generates. (Explain the columns of the generated CSVs)
4. Link GitHub repositories in the DMP!
5. Provide links to all your DOIs in the metadata of your DMP submission.